

A New Hybrid K-Mean-Quick Reduct Algorithm for Gene Selection

E. N. Sathishkumar, K. Thangavel, T. Chandrasekhar

Abstract—Feature selection is a process to select features which are more informative. It is one of the important steps in knowledge discovery. The problem is that all genes are not important in gene expression data. Some of the genes may be redundant, and others may be irrelevant and noisy. Here a novel approach is proposed Hybrid K-Mean-Quick Reduct (KMQR) algorithm for gene selection from gene expression data. In this study, the entire dataset is divided into clusters by applying K-Means algorithm. Each cluster contains similar genes. The high class discriminated genes has been selected based on their degree of dependence by applying Quick Reduct algorithm to all the clusters. Average Correlation Value (ACV) is calculated for the high class discriminated genes. The clusters which have the ACV value as 1 is determined as significant clusters, whose classification accuracy will be equal or high when comparing to the accuracy of the entire dataset. The proposed algorithm is evaluated using WEKA classifiers and compared. The proposed work shows that the high classification accuracy.

Keywords—Clustering, Gene Selection, K-Mean-Quick Reduct, Rough Sets.

I. INTRODUCTION

FEATURE selection, is the process of reducing dimensionality by removing irrelevant features. Dimensionality reduction in gene expression data can be critical for a number of reasons. First, for large number of genes or feature set, the processing of all available genes may be computationally infeasible. Second, many of the available features may be redundant and noise-dominated or irrelevant to the classification task at hand. Third, high-dimensionality is also a problem if the number of variables is much larger than the number of data points available. In such a scenario, dimensionality reduction is crucial in order to overcome the curse of dimensionality [7], [11] and allow for meaningful data analysis.

For the above reasons, feature selection is important for gene expression data analysis. A problem with gene expression analysis is often the selection of significant variables (feature selection) within the data set that would enable accurate classification of the data to some output classes. These variables may be potential diagnostic markers too. There are good reasons for reducing the large number of

variables: First, an opportunity to scrutinize individual genes for further medical treatment and drug development. Second, dimension reduction to reduce the computational cost. Third, reducing the number of redundant and unnecessary variables can improve inference and classification. Fourth, more interpretable features or characteristics that can help identify and monitor the target diseases or functions types.

In this paper, gene or features will be selected from a group, such that the genes in a group will be similar. Gene clustering identifies groups of genes that exhibit similar expression profiles across samples. Clustering is a widely used technique for analysis of gene expression data. Most clustering methods group genes based on the distances, while few methods group according to the similarities of the distributions of the gene expression levels. Clustering is the process of finding groups of objects such that the objects in a group will be similar (or related) to one another and different from (or unrelated to) the objects in other groups. A good clustering method will produce high quality clusters with high intra-cluster similarity and low inter-cluster similarity. The quality of a clustering result depends on both the similarity measure used by the method and its implementation and also by its ability to discover some and all of the hidden patterns [16].

Feature Selection algorithm aims at finding out a subset of the most representative features according to some objective function in discrete space. The algorithms of FS are always greedy. Our feature selection will be based on rough set; The Rough set approach to feature selection consists in selecting a subset of features which can predict the classes as well as the original set of features. The optimal criterion for Rough set feature selection is to find shortest or minimal reducts while obtaining high quality classifiers based on the selected features. In this paper, we introduce a combinational method using K-Means clustering and rough set attribute reduction (Quick Reduct) for single gene selection.

This paper is organized as follows. The next section describes about various methods and in section III briefs the proposed gene selection algorithm. In Section IV, experimental results are listed. The discussions of these results are given. Section V briefs about WEKA classification and its classification results. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in Section VI.

II. METHODS

A. K-Means Clustering

One of the most popular clustering methods is K-Means clustering algorithm. It generates k points as initial centroids arbitrarily, where k is a user specified parameter. Each point is

E. N. Sathishkumar is with the Computer Science Department, Periyar University, Salem, Tamilnadu - 636 011 (phone: +91-9790408041, e-mail: en.sathishkumar@yahoo.in).

K. Thangavel is Head of the Department in Computer Science Department, Periyar University, Salem, Tamilnadu - 636 011, India (e-mail: drktvelu@yahoo.com).

T. Chandrasekhar is with the Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem, Tamilnadu - 636 011, India (e-mail: ch_ansekh80@rediffmail.com).

then assigned to the cluster with the closest centroid. Then the centroid of each cluster is updated by taking the mean of the data points of each cluster. Some data points may move from one cluster to other cluster. Again we calculate new centroids and assign the data points to the suitable clusters. We repeat the assignment and update the centroids, until convergence criteria is met i.e., no point changes clusters, or equivalently, until the centroids remain the same. In this algorithm mostly Euclidean distance is used to find distance between data points and centroids [2]. Pseudo code for the k-means clustering algorithm is described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: K-Means clustering algorithm [18]

Require: $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n\}$ // Set of n data points.
 K - Number of desired clusters

Ensure: A set of K clusters.

Steps:

1. Arbitrarily choose k data points from D as initial centroids;
 2. **Repeat**
 Assign each point d_i to the cluster which has the closest centroid;
 Calculate the new mean for each cluster;
- Until** convergence criteria is met.
-

B. K-means Discretization

Many data mining techniques often require that the attributes of the data sets are discrete. Given that most of the experimental data are continuous, not discrete, the discretization of the continuous attributes is an important issue. The goal of discretization is to reduce the number of possible values a continuous attribute takes by partitioning them into a number of intervals. K-Means discretization method is used in this paper, in gene expression data set each gene attribute are clustered with K-Means, replaces the attribute values with the cluster membership labels. These labels will be act as discrete values for gene expression data set.

C. Quick Reduct Algorithm

Rough set theory [17] is a formal mathematical tool that can be applied to reducing the dimensionality of dataset. The rough set attribute reduction method removes redundant input attributes from dataset of discrete values, all the while making sure that no information is lost. The reduction of attributes is achieved by comparing equivalence relations generated by sets of attributes. Attributes are removed so that the reduced set provides the same quality of classification as the original. A reduct is defined as a subset R of the conditional attribute set C such that $\gamma_R(D) = \gamma_C(D)$. A given dataset may have many attribute reduct sets, so the set R of all reducts is defined as:

$$R_{all} = \{X | X \subseteq C, \gamma_X(D) = \gamma_C(D); \gamma_{X-\{a\}}(D) \neq \gamma_X(D), \forall a \in X\}. \quad (1)$$

The intersection of all the sets in R_{all} is called the core, the elements of which are those attributes that cannot be

eliminated without introducing more contradictions to the representation of the dataset. For many tasks (for example, feature selection), a reduct of minimal cardinality is ideally searched for a single element of the reduct set $R_{min} \subseteq R_{all}$:

$$R_{min} = \{X | X \in R_{all}, \forall Y \in R_{all}, |X| \leq |Y|\}. \quad (2)$$

The Quick Reduct algorithm shown below, it searches for a minimal subset without exhaustively generating all possible subsets. The search begins with an empty subset; attributes which result in the greatest increase in the rough set dependency value that is added iteratively. This process continues until the search produces its maximum possible dependency value for that dataset $\gamma_C(D)$. Note that this type of search does not guarantee a minimal subset and may only discover a local minimum. Such techniques may be found in [1], [7], [8], [14], [17].

Algorithm 2: Quick Reduct(C, D)

C , the set of all conditional features;
 D , the set of decision features.

- (a) $R \leftarrow \{\}$
 - (b) **Do**
 - (c) $T \leftarrow R$
 - (d) $\forall x \in (C-R)$
 - (e) **if** $\gamma_{R \cup \{x\}}(D) > \gamma_T(D)$
 Where $\gamma_R(D) = \frac{card(POS_R(D))}{card(U)}$
 - (f) $T \leftarrow R \cup \{x\}$
 - (g) $R \leftarrow T$
 - (h) **until** $\gamma_R(D) == \gamma_C(D)$
 - (i) **return** R
-

D. Average Correlation Value

Average Correlation Value is used to evaluate the homogeneity of a cluster. Matrix $A = (A_{ij})$ has the ACV which is defined by the following function,

$$ACV(A) = \max \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m |c_{row_{ij}}| - m}{m^2 - m}, \frac{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^n |c_{col_{pq}}| - n}{n^2 - n} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $C_{row_{ij}}$ is the correlation coefficient between rows i and j , $C_{col_{pq}}$ is the correlation coefficient between columns p and q , ACV approaching 1 denote a significant cluster. Such technique may be found in [12].

III. HYBRID K-MEAN-QUICK REDUCT (KMQR) ALGORITHM

The proposed KMQR algorithm logically consists of three steps: (i) grouping the similar genes, (ii) feature selection from group, (iii) finding ACV and selecting representative features.

The purpose of the algorithm is to select a subset of features $R = \{RG_1, RG_2, \dots, RG_r\}$ from the original gene set $G = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ where n is the dimension of gene feature vectors and $r < n$ is the number of selected features that having ACV = 1. A feature G_{best} is included in the subset R , if for this G_{best} , the subset R gives the highest classification accuracy. The

algorithm of KMQR method is described as follows.

Algorithm 3: Hybrid K-Mean-Quick Reduct (KMQR)

Inputs: Gene expression data contains n genes and a m class variable, $G = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ and $D = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_m\}$
Output: G_{best} – Selected gene
 Step 1: set $k=5$ and $G_{best} \leftarrow \{\}$
 Step 2: Do, Gene wise cluster
 $GC_i = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_q\}$, according to Alg.1
 here $i=1$ to k , where $\sum_{i=1}^k GC_i(q) == n$
 End
 Step 3: Discretize the GC_i by applying K-means Discretization
 Step 4: for $i= 1$ to k
 Do, Quick Reduct(GC_i, D) to select
 $RC_i = \{R_1, R_2, \dots, R_r\}$ according to Alg.2
 where $RC_i \subseteq GC_i$
 End
 End
 Step 5: Compute ACV for all refined RC_i according to Eqs.3
 Step 6: Collect all the genes from clusters, where $ACV=1$
 $R_k = \{RC_i / ACV(RC_i) = 1\} = \{RG_1, RG_2, \dots, RG_r\}$
 where $r =$ no. of genes in $acv=1$ clusters
 Step 7: Repeat step 2 to 6, for $k = 7, 10$ and etc.
 where $k =$ no. of clusters we need.
 Step 8: Let $G_{best} = \bigcap_{k \in Rk} R_k$
 Step 9: Return G_{best}

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Data Sets

We use leukemia data set which is available in the website: <http://datam.i2r.a-star.edu.sg/datasets/krbd/> [15]. Our initial leukemia data set consisted of 38 bone marrow samples (27 ALL, 11 AML) obtained from acute leukemia patients at the time of diagnosis. RNA prepared from bone marrow mononuclear cells was hybridized to high-density oligonucleotide microarrays, produced by Affymetrix and containing probes over 7129 from 6817 human genes [19].

B. Cluster Analysis and Feature Selection

Gene clustering identifies group of genes that exhibit similar expression profiles across samples. K-Means clustering is used to cluster the similar characteristics of genes GC_i . Before clustering, need to specify the number of clusters. The optimal number of clusters is difficult to determine, because it may depend on different sets of genes under investigation. In this study, the number of clusters is chosen to be five, seven and ten ($k=5, 7, 10$), then leukemia data set will divide k number of groups using K-Means clustering techniques. After clustering, features or genes will be selected from a similar gene cluster GC_i . Rough Quick Reduct has been used as feature selection method. The data studied by rough set are mainly organized in the form of decision tables. One decision table can be represented as $S = (U, A=GC_i \cup D)$, where U is the set of samples in cluster GC_i ($i=1$ to k), GC_i the

condition attribute set and D the decision attribute set. We can represent every gene expression data with the decision table like Table I.

TABLE I
 ROUGH SET DATA DECISION TABLE

Samples	Cluster GC_i (Condition attributes)				Decision attributes
	Gene1	Gene 2	...	Gene q	Class label
1	$g(1,1)$	$g(1,2)$...	$g(1,q)$	Class(1)
2	$g(2,1)$	$g(2,2)$...	$g(2,q)$	Class(2)
...
p	$g(p,1)$	$g(p,2)$...	$g(p,q)$	Class(p)

In the decision table, there are p samples and q genes in cluster GC_i . Every sample is assigned to one class label. Each gene is a condition attribute and each class is a decision attribute. $g(p, q)$ signifies the expression level of gene q in sample p [15]. Before applying feature selection algorithm all the conditional attributes (samples) are discretized using K-Means discretization. After feature selection, to evaluate the Average Correlation Value for selected genes from each cluster. ACV approaching 1 denote a significant cluster and it is evaluating the homogeneity of a cluster. Tables II-IV show the selected genes from particular cluster by applying Quick Reduct and Average Correlation Value for that genes.

TABLE II
 SELECTED GENES WHEN CLUSTER $k=5$

Cluster	All Genes (GC_i)	QR Selected Genes (RC_i)	ACV
Cluster 1	39	#19, #44, #930, #1841	0.6011
Cluster 2	873	#220, #6855	1
Cluster 3	6025	#4, #3252	1
Cluster 4	74	#1674, #3452, #4017	0.6767
Cluster 5	118	#543, #1962, #3361	0.6266

Table II, depict the similar expression genes when $k=5$, and shows selected genes (RC_i) after applied Quick Reduct. Based on Average Correlation Values, we determine cluster 2 and 3 are significant clusters R_k . In that cluster genes having high classification accuracy compare to other genes.

TABLE III
 SELECTED GENES WHEN CLUSTER $k=7$

Cluster	All Genes (GC_i)	QR Selected Genes (RC_i)	ACV
Cluster 1	694	#952, #5350, #6194	0.6559
Cluster 2	5063	#29, #1144	1
Cluster 3	61	#1677, #4116, #5938	0.6280
Cluster 4	1007	#79, #3252	1
Cluster 5	38	#44, #47, #896, #445	0.5079
Cluster 6	65	#42, #45, #563	0.6188
Cluster 7	201	#1962, #2288	1

Table III shows similar expression genes when $k=7$ and depict selected genes (RC_i) after Quick Reduct. Based on Average Correlation Values, we determine Cluster 2, 4 and 7 are significant clusters.

TABLE IV
 SELECTED GENES WHEN CLUSTER $k=10$

Cluster	All Genes (G _c)	QR Selected Genes (R _c)	ACV
Cluster 1	38	#46, #930, #4178	0.6807
Cluster 2	1491	#79, #3252	1
Cluster 3	401	#952, #1884, #6194	0.6380
Cluster 4	434	#67, #412, #6041	0.7196
Cluster 5	10	Non	Non
Cluster 6	1	Non	Non
Cluster 7	51	#746, #1775, #4116	0.6654
Cluster 8	65	#45, #291, #1674	0.7056
Cluster 9	114	#52, #1962, #2121	0.6269
Cluster 10	4524	#587, #1902	1

Table IV illustrates the similar genes when $k=10$ and depict R_c that are selected genes after Quick Reduct. We determine Cluster 2 and 10 are significant cluster (R_k) based on ACV. All the R_k sub set genes have the classification accuracy higher than 88.2353%.

V. WEKA CLASSIFICATION

The classifier tool WEKA [1], [11], [13] is open source java based machine-learning. It brings together many machine learning algorithm and tools under a common frame work. The WEKA is a well known package of data mining tools which provides a variety of known, well maintained classifying algorithms. This allows us to do experiments with several kinds of classifiers quickly and easily. The tool is used to perform benchmark experiment. Some of the classifiers we used in our experiment are bayes.NaiveBayes, trees.J48, rules.Decision Table and lazy.K-Star.

TABLE V
 CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY OF GENES WHEN $k=5$

Classifier	Entire data 7129 genes (G)	QR selected 14 genes	ACV=1 4 genes (R _k)
Naïve	94.1176	97.0588	97.0588
D. Table	88.2353	94.1176	94.1176
J48	91.1765	97.0588	97.0588
K-Star	58.8235	94.1176	97.0588

Fig. 1 Classification Accuracy when cluster $k=5$

Fig. 1, Denotes classification accuracy for leukemia data when cluster $k=5$. We obtained fourteen genes from entire genes by applying Quick Reduct. Out of the fourteen genes

which genes having ACV=1 that four genes are selected as best R_k. The classification accuracy for those four; #3252, #220, #6855 and #4 genes is equal or high when compared to entire genes (7129) and Quick Reduct selected genes.

TABLE VI
 CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY OF GENES WHEN $k=7$

Classifier	Entire data 7129 genes (G)	QR selected 19 genes	ACV=1 6 genes (R _k)
Naïve	94.1176	97.0588	97.0588
D. Table	88.2353	91.1765	94.1176
J48	91.1765	97.0588	88.2353
K-Star	58.8235	94.1176	97.0588

Fig. 2 Classification Accuracy when cluster $k=7$

Fig. 2, Denotes classification accuracy of leukemia data when $k=7$. We obtained nineteen genes from entire genes by applying Quick Reduct. Out of the nineteen genes which genes having ACV=1 that six genes are selected as high class discriminated genes R_k. The classification accuracy for those six; #3252, #29, #1144, #79, #1962 and #2288 genes is equal or high when compared to entire genes and Quick Reduct selected genes.

TABLE VII
 CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY OF GENES WHEN $k=10$

Classifier	Entire data 7129 genes (G)	QR selected 22 genes	ACV=1 4 genes (R _k)
Naïve	94.1176	97.0588	94.1176
D. Table	88.2353	94.1176	94.1176
J48	91.1765	91.1765	91.1765
K-Star	58.8235	94.1176	97.0588

Fig. 3 Classification Accuracy when cluster $k=10$

Fig. 3 depicts classification accuracy of leukemia data when $k=10$. We obtained twenty two genes from entire genes by applying Quick Reduct. Out of the twenty two genes which genes having $ACV=1$ that four genes are selected (R_k). The classification accuracy for those four; #3252, #79, #587 and #1902 genes is equal or high when compared to entire genes and Quick Reduct selected genes.

TABLE VIII

MARKER GENE SELECTED FROM SIGNIFICANT CLUSTERS GENES		
Cluster	R_k Genes	Selected gene
Cluster $k=5$	#220,#6855,#4,#3252	
Cluster $k=7$	#29,#1144,#79,#3252,#1962,#2288	#3252
Cluster $k=10$	#79,#3252,#587,#1902	(G_{best})

Table VIII shows, in the leukemia dataset, when cluster $k=5$, gene #3252, #220, #6855 and #4 are identified; when $k=7$, gene #3252, #29, #1144, #79, #1962 and #2288 are identified; when $k=10$, gene #3252, #79, #587 and #1902 are identified. Among the significant clusters ($ACV=1$) genes have the classification accuracy higher than 88.2353%. Finally, we get $G_{best} = \bigcap_{k \in R_k} R_k$ is gene #3252 has 97.0588% accuracy and which is common to all experiment. We denote the expression level of gene x by $g(x)$. Two decision rules induced by gene #3252 are:

If $g(\#3252) > 643$, then AML; If $g(\#3252) \leq 643$, then ALL.

A. Comparison of Classification Results

The leukemia dataset has been well studied by many researchers [3]-[6], [8]-[10]. Although there are a few reports on the use of a single gene to distinguish the AML from the ALL, a majority of investigators conduct the classification with more than one gene, even tens or hundreds. In [15], the authors present the classification outcomes of 31 out of 34 samples correctly classified with one common gene (#4847): we correctly classify 33 out of 34 samples using a selected gene (#3252). Classification accuracy for existing and proposed method selected single genes shown in Table IX.

TABLE IX

COMPARISON BETWEEN EXISTING AND PROPOSED METHOD		
Classifier	Existing Method gene #4847	Proposed KMQR gene #3252
Naïve	91.1765	97.0588
D.Table	85.2941	91.1765
J48	88.2353	91.1765
K-Star	91.1765	97.0588

Fig. 4 Classification Accuracy of Existing and Proposed method

Regarding leukemia datasets, the best classification results reported in our and existing works are shown in Table IX and Fig. 4, respectively. These tables demonstrate that our KMQR algorithm perform comparatively well in leukemia dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION

The work has been proposed for improving the gene selection method in a simple and efficient way. Here a novel approach KMQR has been proposed by combining clustering and rough set attribute reduction together for gene selection from gene expression data. Informative genes are selected using their classification accuracy. K-means clustering, Rough Quick Reduct and Average Correlation Value methods are studied and implemented successfully for gene selection. The proposed work gives sparse and interpretable classification accuracy, compared to other gene selection method on leukemia gene expression data set. The classification accuracy of genes has been done using WEKA classifier. In compare with other gene selection methods, our method is simple, effective and robust.

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Currently he is working as Guest lecturer, Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem, Tamilnadu, India. His area of interests includes Medical Data Mining, Rough Set and Bioinformatics.

E. N. Sathishkumar was born in Namakkal at 1986, Tamilnadu, India. He received his Master of Science in Information Technology from Anna University, Coimbatore in 2009. He obtained his Master of Philosophy from the Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem, India in 2011. He is pursuing his Ph.D in Computer Science at Periyar University under the guidance of Dr. K. Thangavel.

His area of interests includes Data Mining, Rough Set, Bioinformatics and Neural Network.

K. Thangavel was born in Namakkal at 1964, Tamilnadu, India. He received his Master of Science from the Department of Mathematics, Bharathidasan University in 1986, and Master of Computer Applications Degree from Madurai Kamaraj University, India in 2001. He obtained his Ph.D. Degree from the Department of Mathematics, Gandhigram Rural Institute-Deemed University, Gandhigram, India in 1999.

Currently he is working as Professor and Head, Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem. He is a recipient of Tamilnadu Scientist award for the year 2009. His area of interests includes Medical Image Processing, Bioinformatics, Artificial Intelligence, Neural Network, Fuzzy logic, Data Mining and Rough Set.

T. Chandrasekhar was born in Karur at 1980, Tamilnadu, India. He is received the Master of Science in information technology and management in 2003 and his M.Phil (Computer Science) Degree in 2004, from Bharathidasan University, Trichy, India. He is pursuing his Ph.D in Bharathiar University in Computer Science under the guidance of Dr. K. Thangavel.